

Sampling protocol for aquatic fungi from marine, river and lake water and sediment

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Required fieldwork material:

1. Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver
2. Instrument(s) for measuring water temperature, DO, depth and other parameters available (pH, conductivity, etc)
3. Secchi disc
4. Water sampler or sampling bottle, collection bucket
5. Optional: sediment corer
6. Sterile 1 L bottles (preferentially polyethylene, PE or glass) for water chemistry samples
7. 2 x sterile 50 mL tubes (e.g. centrifuge tubes) for sediment samples
8. Sterile spoon or syringe with cut inlet/outlet side for small size corer
9. Luer-Lock Sterivex filters
10. Luer-Lock caps
11. 60 ml luer lock syringe
12. 1 x small syringe (3 ml) for adding storage and lysis buffer
13. storage buffer (Longmire's buffer)
14. Disposable gloves.
15. Parafilm or insulating tape to cover the screw caps (to avoid leaking during the transport)
16. Transparent tape to cover all labels
17. Waterproof marker pen, pencil
18. Labels for samples (preferably preprinted)
19. Field protocol/book to record any supporting information during the fieldwork
20. a cooler box with ice or ice blocks to keep the samples in the dark and cold.

SX – sterivex; **S** – sediment; **W** – water

All the samples should be labelled with their unique name. Same name in the field protocol and on the label.

NB! Labels should be preprinted or if it is not possible, marked with PENCIL and the label should be covered with tape!

SAMPLING WATER for STERIVEX and chemistry analyses

1. Walk carefully (try to prevent bottom sediments rising) to the water depth of at least 40-50 cm.
2. Record the GPS coordinates of sampling site, mark them to the notebook.
3. Measure the abiotic parameters like temperature, DO, Secchi depth and other parameters available (pH, conductivity, etc) from the surface and bottom, record and note the values.
4. Put on disposable gloves (non-powdered).
5. Rinse the sampling bottle or sampler 3 times with surface water.

6. Place the bottle(s) approximately 20-30 cm below the water surface and fill with water.
7. Collect the water into the collection bucket
8. Fill 1 L for chemical analyses
9. Filter the water on STERIVEX filters until clogging (Expected filtration volumes: 50–100 ml for hypertrophic water, 100-250 ml for eutrophic water and up to 1000 ml for oligotrophic water)

* Sterivex filtering is recommended to be performed immediately after sampling.

- Open the prepacked kit and put on clean gloves.
- Fill the 60 ml syringe with collected water, screw on the filter inlet and push water through
- Repeat the step until the filter clogs and record the volume of filtered water
- Push air through the filter with an air-filled 60 ml syringe to expel any remaining water and dry the filter
- Uncap and attach a small syringe with storage buffer to the inlet, hold the filter with outlet upwards and carefully fill the filter with preservative buffer until the buffer starts to leak from the capsule
- Place the luer lock cap on filter outlet and fill all the rest of the capsule with storage buffer
- Place luer lock cap on filter inlet
- Write the sample name on the sticker (use pencil) and paste it on the Sterivex filter. Secure the sticker on the tube with tape.
- Fill the sample information with the data (Sample name, Date, Latitude, Longitude, water temperature and depth, Vol of filtered water)
- Place the filter small zip-lock bag
- Storage the sample in the dark at room temperature until further steps

SAMPLING – SEDIMENT

1. Label the two 50-ml tubes.
2. Walk to the water depth of 40-50 cm – preferentially at the same point as for water samples.
3. If not, record the GPS coordinates of the sampling site and mark these in a notebook.
4. Put on disposable gloves (non-powdered).
5. Rinse the two labelled 50 ml tubes 3 times with surface water.
6. Fill both tubes to half of their volume with sediment by pushing the tubes to the sediment layer preferably at 5-10 cm sediment depth OR Use sediment corer to take the top 15 cm of sediment, fill two 50 mL tubes to half of their volume with upper sediment layer)
7. Pour off water and surplus material and fill another half of the tube with storage buffer ASAP.
8. Mix thoroughly by turning the tubes carefully 6x upside down
9. Secure the cap with parafilm or insulation tape to prevent leaking.
10. Label all the tubes accordingly
11. Cover the labels with transparent tape to protect these from leakage during the transportation and storage
12. Keep the samples in dark

Obligatory information to be recorded and filled in the report file (provided by organisers).

1. Unique sample name*
2. Name and contacts of collector
3. Name of the waterbody
4. GPS coordinates in WGS84 system: preferred format DD.DDDDD North, DD.DDDDD East
5. Sampling date: preferred format YYYY-MM-DD
6. Filtration volume (ml) for water samples
7. Any other supporting information
 - Sampling depth
 - Overall depth
 - Secchi depth
 - Water temperature
 - Water pH and other abiotic parameters available
 - Water dissolved oxygen
 - Water Ctotal, Ntotal, Ptotal, K, Mg, Ca concentrations **OR** send 100 ml of water to us for analysis

* give a unique sample name for the sample (column - sample_name) - This is ID code, that should include **country code** (example EE-Estonia), **team code** (example UT- University of Tartu), **code for the waterbody along with the sample type, and parallel no** (example – PEI_SX1 – Lake Peipsi sterivex1). Unique sample names for Lake Peipsi could be EE_UT_PEI_SX1, EE_UT_PEI_SX2 (SX1 - sterivex sample 1, SX2 - sterivex sample 2).

CONTACT DETAILS

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Please fill the data form (sent after registration) with supporting information and metadata. All questions can be addressed to kristel.panksep@emu.ee.

SHIPPING ADDRESS

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